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History of Oil Drilling in La Jolla • Secret Garden Tour Blooms in May
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Oil Drilling In La Jolla: A Slippery Business Through History

by Mikala Narlock

"If there is one spot in all California that has served more than another to spread the fair fame of the state throughout the world, and particularly throughout the eastern states, it is the city of San Diego. Nestling on the slope of the golden foothills of the coast range, upon the shores of what is perhaps the most picturesque bay in the world, bathed continually in the warm sunshine of the semi-tropics, tempered by the ever balmy breeze from the Pacific, it is at once an ideal resort for the tourist and traveler, who, in his journeying around and about the earth, has hitherto sought in vain for perfection of scene and climate."

This excerpt, from the "Los Angeles Daily Herald" of May 31, 1902, holds true even today, as San Diego is not only a prime tourist destination, but the choice of home for many. However, in the early 20th century, San Diego, and by extension La Jolla, was shaping up in a different way, as was all of Southern California. Though the California Gold Rush in 1848 was what drove many of the settlers out West, it was not the prospect of gold that was bracing to change the view of the ocean, but the search for. . .OIL!

The Native Americans and European explorers had noted the presence of oil and gas seeps in Southern California well before the turn of the 19th century, using asphaltum to seal baskets and water bottles, repair ships, fashion their weapons, and as kerosene in place of whale oil in lamps. Yet, it was not until Summerland, near Santa Barbara, that the first production of oil truly began. In the late 1890's several residents digging wells for water found oil, and filled their buckets with the black gold to sell around the community. Soon after, the search for oil began on a larger scale. In 1897 the first well was built on a pier just off the Santa Barbara coast.

In these early days the "Los Angeles Daily Herald" devoted entire pages to updates in the oil fields along with advertisements for numerous companies selling their bonds at 50 cents apiece. One section, titled "News From the Oil Fields and the Mines," exclusively covered the oil wells and the mines, providing regular updates on progress, such as the depth of the drill, if oil had been reached, and what depth was expected for the company to find oil.

On Sept. 13th, 1900, the Herald released reports of wells in San Diego. Instead of broadly speaking about the potential oil in San Diego County, one article specifically mentions La Jolla and the "La Jolla Oil company." It was reported that a minor 100-ft. well was dug in preparation for a rig, which was set to arrive on the 15th of September, but the drill was not expected to operate until just before the first of October. In an article dated Oct. 20, 1900, it is stated that drilling has not yet begun as the machinery only recently arrived, and the experts at the well, which has now reached a depth of 130 feet, declared that the company could expect to hit oil well before the 500-ft. marker. The next update of Jan. 3rd, 1901, when is simply stated that there continued to be steady work with "indications proving more satisfactory every day." On Jan. 22nd, another article notes that the work in La Jolla continues in a satisfactory fashion as they reach a depth of 700 feet, over two hundred feet past the depth

Norwalk CA c.1940

Courtesy Library of Congress

experts predicted would yield oil, with still promising indications. In conclusion, however, there is nothing to indicate that oil was ever found or that the drilling process continued beyond the first year of the new century.

In 1920, an oil shortage hit California, as the demand for oil increased, in correlation with the increase of trucks and tractors throughout the state, yet supply did not. However, less than a year before the release of this article, there is a small paragraph in the Oct. 10th, 1919, issue of the "La Jolla Journal," which, though short, states that "the area surrounding La Jolla" was being investigated by geologists seeking oil. Rumors spread of a well to be erected on top of the mesa "between the Biological Station and Torrey Pines" within two or three weeks. For whatever reasons, though, the rumors of a well and drilling never came to fruition.

Five years later some of the gooey "gold" actually appeared oozing to the surface. The "Los Angeles Herald" reported "some oozing, oily substance, topped with iridescent slime" surfacing on the D.W. Rannels' property at 7826 Herschel Ave. It caused a great stir in La Jolla and everyone ran to look at the slime, but it ended at about that, perhaps leaving a few people with ideas for horror movies down the line and, definitely, dirty boots. The next person reporting a slimy substance on his land in the San Diego area was a Colonel D. S. Roscoe. That was in Vista and also produced nothing but another momentary mess.

Before the 1950's, the potential effects of oil wells on tourism

Summerland 1920

Venice CA 1952

remained primarily unconsidered. But a growing awareness of the natural environments in the 1950s and '60s produced some new thoughts: a beach dotted with oil wells is not only aesthetically unappealing, but it is also a serious health hazard, affecting both the lives of those frolicking in the ocean as well as those breathing in the toxic air, not to mention the disastrous environmental effects that are occurring in the ocean and the air. In the 1950's, La Jolla began to take these factors into consideration. In November of 1954, more surveys were done to assess the potential oil in La Jolla. One particular survey took place off they coast of La Jolla, and suggested that if oil were discovered, wells would be placed in the ocean, disrupting the scenic ocean views. Just before this surveying began, the voters decided to return "the tidelands to the state of California," which then had "the sole power of leasing rights to private oil companies,"

leaving the city with virtually nothing to say in the matter.

In January of 1955, however, the city was called to action by Hugh B. Martin, an attorney, geologist, and oil consultant who was employed by Santa Barbara, seeking support from La Jolla. On January 13, an article was released in the "La Jolla Journal" expressing concern that if oil was found and drilled in Santa Barbara, it could happen in La Jolla. Martin was seeking the support of large organizations, such as the La Jolla Town Council or the La Jolla Kiwanis Club in order to prevent the drilling, and the Town Council unanimously voted to "enter the case as a 'friend of the court.'" In the next issue of the "La Jolla Journal," there is a beautiful image of La Jolla's shoreline, with the title "This Beautiful Swimming Beach Could Be Oil Soaked," in an attempt to call the citizens of La Jolla to action. Numerous companies and

social groups sought to assume control over their city, at least in the matter of drilling for oil. It appears to have mixed results, for drilling for oil began in Santa Barbara, yet the mentions of oil in the "La Jolla Journal" and the "La Jolla Light" do not resume until 1969.

In bold letters across the first page of the now combined newspapers the town council asked for the state of California as well as the U.S. Department of Interior to stop drilling. This was largely in response to an oil spill in Santa Barbara. The community of La Jolla was concerned that its beaches would marred in the same way as Santa Barbara's. As La Jolla, and all of San Diego, was dependent on the beach to draw tourists, a potential threat to the beach was a threat to the economy. Two weeks later, California Lieutenant Governor Ed Reinecke called for tighter laws in terms of offshore drilling. The regulations at this time were for the Gulf of Mexico, where the oil deposits were miles off-shore. With pollution of beaches, such as waste discharge and sewage outfalls, there was concern as to not only tourism, but also to the potential health risks to those enjoying the ocean.

Less than a month later, a small article titled "Town Council Gets Replies to Oil Resolution," Senator Cranston states that he has proposed a bill to "suspend all drilling off the California Coast until there are firm assurances that oil operations will not endanger the beaches and marine resources."

Although Cranston's bill never passed, a great deal of public awareness had been roused, an awareness that continues today when the subject of oil in La Jolla, on or off-shore, is broached.

Narlock, a University of San Diego graduate, wrote this article while serving as an intern at the La Jolla Historical Society. Archivist/curator Mike Mishler also contributed.